

The effect of leadership and training on performance 'Start Up Tani Hub' employees

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Abstract

An organization/company requires a synergy between all elements in it, especially the human resource factor. This study aims to determine whether there is a relationship between leadership and training on employee performance. The sample tested in this study were employees of 'Start Up Tani Hub'. The data used is through the activities of distributing questionnaires to these employees. The analytical method used is multiple regression analysis with data processing using the SPSS program. The results of this study indicate that leadership and training have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This study provides input to enrich the theory of the relationship between leadership and training on employee performance.

Keywords: Employee Performance; Human Resources; Leadership; Training

1 Introduction

An organization / company requires synergy between all elements in it, especially the human resource factor. In the development of an increasingly fast and sophisticated business environment that demands innovation and creativity in order to create relationships that are able to create solutions for business partners, companies need to strengthen the quality of human resources in this case is the performance of their employees. To mobilize human resources to be able to provide optimal output, an effective leader is needed so that the company's expectations can be achieved. Leaders who are able to influence and direct their members are leaders who are recognized by the company because their strategy in leading can bring the company to realize its goals. The success or failure of an organization is determined by the quality of a leader, both business-oriented and public organizations. Leaders also play a very important role in formulating and implementing organizational strategies because each leader has a different way of influencing and directing his members, this is inseparable from his abilities and personality. The ability of a leader can be seen from his way of thinking in the long term which includes planning, organizing, mobilizing and supervising so that all planning can run well.

The training aims to improve employee performance to achieve predetermined work results. Performance improvement can be done by improving the knowledge, skills or attitudes of the employees themselves towards their work, while training is an effort related to increasing the abilities or skills of an employee. According to [1], training can be interpreted as a process that is provided by the company to employees through training professionals with the aim of improving work abilities in each field.

Training as a solution to performance problems that have been faced by a company because the training itself is an effort by the company in increasing employee motivation and one of the employee needs, especially the need for self-actualization when viewed in Masslow's theory of needs and growth needs when viewed from Signal theory.

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Performance can be seen and measured if an employee already has criteria or benchmark success standards that have been set by the company so that performance in carrying out its functions does not stand alone but is related to the leadership role and training provided by the company. Employee performance determines the direction of success

from the company in achieving the expected goals and this needs to be supported by several factors that can affect employee performance, namely with effective leadership that is able to influence its members and support the company in providing continuous training in order to create high motivation from its employees and will also have implications on employee performance.

Based on this description, it is the reason for researchers to conduct research related to the influence of leadership and training on motivation and their implications for the performance of the employees of 'Start Up Tani Hub'.

2 Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

2.1 Leadership

Leadership according to [2] can be defined as a way that will be used and applied by a leader in influencing the behavior of its members or what is called a leadership style. Leadership style is a behavioral norm that has been used by leaders when trying to influence the behavior of their members and this leadership style will differ from one leader to another because it is in accordance with the abilities and personality of the leader himself [3].

There are four indicators of leadership according to [4] including the following:

- Maturity and breadth of social relations. A leader tends to be mature if he has stable emotions in guiding employees or making decisions and has broad attention to social activities. A leader also has a desire to be respected and appreciated.
- Motivation and Drive for Achievement. A leader has a strong motivational drive for achievement and strives for intrinsic rather than extrinsic rewards.
- Attitudes of Human Relations. A successful leader is a leader who wants to recognize the self-esteem and respect of his employees. Leaders are more oriented to their employees than to the company's products.
- Intelligence. In general, leaders have a higher level of intelligence than the people they lead.

2.2 Training

According to [5] that training can cause a reaction to increase the abilities and skills of employees in this case, increasing abilities and skills will make it easier to carry out tasks according to the work that has been determined. Training can connect the gap between the performance possessed by the standardization that has been expected by the company because in the training process not only skills will be developed but also the company will be helped in operating better and ready to compete [6].

The training itself is related to improving the abilities and skills of employees who have occupied certain positions or tasks. Emphasis in training is the task to be carried out (job orientation). In addition, training generally emphasizes psychomotor abilities even though they are based on knowledge and attitudes.

2.3 Employee Performance

Figure 1 Research Conceptual Framework

According to [7], performance is a function of the driving force and ability to complete the tasks and responsibilities of an employee who should have a certain degree of willingness and level of ability. However, the willingness and skills of

an employee are not effective enough in carrying out work without a clear understanding of what and how to do it. Performance itself is something that is real shown by every employee as a work achievement based on its role in the company so that employee performance is an important thing in the company's efforts to achieve its goals [8].

Hypothesis is as follow:

H1: Leadership has an effect on employee performance

H2: Training has an effect on employee performance

3 Method

The type of research used is quantitative research. The population in this study were all permanent employees of 'Start Up Tani Hub', totaling 60 employees. In this study using a non-probability sampling technique, namely saturated sampling, which is a method of determining the sample if all members of the population are sampled. Saturated sample is also called a census so that the number of samples taken by researchers is 60 respondents who are the entire population.

Researchers used primary data sources obtained directly from data collection using questionnaires distributed to respondents. Respondents' answers to the questionnaire were then recorded and processed using SPSS software.

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Leadership (X1)

The measurement of leadership variables uses a questionnaire that has been given to lecturers. The results of the questionnaire data processing of 60 respondents obtained the highest score of 28, the lowest score of 13 with a range of 15, an average of 21.67, a standard deviation of 3.947 and a variance of 15.582. While the quality of leadership is determined based on 5 categories, namely strongly agree, agree, less agree, disagree, and strongly disagree. Demographic results in the table below:

Table 1 Leadership Variable Feedback Demographic Statistics

N Valid	60
N Missing	0
Mean	21.67
Std. Deviation	3.947
Variance	15.582
Range	15
Minimum	13
Maximum	28

Source: processed field data

4.2 Training (X2)

Measurement of training variables using a questionnaire that has been given to employees. The results of the questionnaire data processing of 60 respondents obtained the highest score of 25, the lowest score of 7 with a range of 18, an average of 17.55, a standard deviation of 3.833 and a variance of 14.692. While the quality of training is determined based on 5 categories, namely strongly agree, agree, less agree, disagree, and strongly disagree. Demographic results in the table below:

Table 2 Training Variable Feedback Demographic Statistics

N Valid	60
N Missing	0
Mean	17.55
Std. Deviation	3.833
Variance	14.692
Range	18
Minimum	7
Maximum	25

Source: processed field data

4.3 Employee Performance (Y)

Measurement of employee performance variables using a questionnaire that has been given to permanent employees. The results of the questionnaire data processing of 60 respondents obtained the highest score of 25, the lowest score of 8 with a range of 17, an average of 19.07 standard deviation of 3.853 and a variance of 14.843. While the quality of employee performance is determined based on 5 categories, namely strongly agree, agree, less agree, disagree, and strongly disagree. Demographic results in the table below:

Table 3 Employee Performance Variable Feedback Demographic Statistics

N Valid	60
N Missing	0
Mean	19.07
Std. Deviation	3.853
Variance	14.843
Range	17
Minimum	8
Maximum	25

Source: processed field data

4.4 Model Analysis

4.4.1. Validity Test

Whether or not a measuring instrument is valid in a study can be obtained from the results of the validity test. In this leadership variable (X1) there are 6 statement items, Training variable (X2) there are 5 statement items, employee performance (Y) there are 5 statement items so that the total question items in this research questionnaire are 16 statement items. The basis for decision making in this validity test if $r\text{-count} > r\text{-table}$ then it is declared valid and if $r\text{-count} \leq r\text{-table}$ then it is declared invalid. Based on the calculation of $df = N - 2$ with an error rate of 5%, it was obtained $r\text{-table}$ with a value of 0.254. The results of the validity test of each variable can be interpreted in the table.

In the table above. the results of the validity test show that all items in the leadership variable statement (X1): numbers X1.1, X1.2, X1.3, X1.4, X1.5 and X1.6 are declared valid because all greater than 0.254.

Table 4 Leadership Validity Test Results Data

X1.1		X1.2	X1.3	X1.4	X1.5	X1.6	X1	
X1.1	Pearson Correlation	1	0.866**	0.719**	0.732**	0.043	-0.057	0.772**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.742	0.663	0.000
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60	60
X1.2	Pearson Correlation	0.866**	1	0.796**	0.795**	-0.022	-0.072	0.781**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000		0.000	0.000	0.866	0.583	0.000
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60	60
X1.3	Pearson Correlation	0.719**	0.796**	1	0.817**	-0.060	-0.143	0.725**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.649	0.277	0.000
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60	60
X1.4	Pearson Correlation	0.732**	0.795**	0.817**	1	-0.027	-0.058	0.760**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000		0.839	0.660	0.000
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60	60
X1.5	Pearson Correlation	0.043	-0.022	-0.060	-0.027	1	0.776**	0.511**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.742	0.866	0.649	0.839		0.000	0.000
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60	60
X1.6	Pearson Correlation	-0.057	-0.072	-0.143	-0.058	0.776**	1	0.452**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.663	0.583	0.277	0.660	0.000		0.000
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60	60
X1	Pearson Correlation	0.772**	0.781**	0.725**	0.760**	0.511**	0.452**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60	60

Source: processed field data

Table 5 Training Validity Test Results Data

X2.1		X2.2	X2.3	X2.4	X2.5	X2	
X2.1	Pearson Correlation	1	0.480**	0.699**	0.524**	0.433**	0.830**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60
X2.2	Pearson Correlation	0.480**	1	0.489**	0.501**	0.567**	0.776**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60
X2.3	Pearson Correlation	0.699**	0.489**	1	0.557**	0.273*	0.796**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.035	0.000
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60
X2.4	Pearson Correlation	0.524**	0.501**	0.557**	1	0.515**	0.771**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.000

	N	60	60	60	60	60	60
X2.5	Pearson Correlation	0.433**	0.567**	0.273*	0.515**	1	0.704**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.001	0.000	0.035	0.000		0.000
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60
X2	Pearson Correlation	0.830**	0.776**	0.796**	0.771**	0.704**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60

Source: processed field data

In the table above. the results of the validity test show that all items in the training variable statement (X2): numbers X2.1, X2.2, X2.3, X2.4 and X2.5 are declared valid because all greater than 0.254.

Table 6 Employee Performance Validity Test Results Data

	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y5	Y	
Y1	Pearson Correlation	1	0.708**	0.625**	0.647**	0.658**	0.839**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60
Y2	Pearson Correlation	0.708**	1	0.764**	0.833**	0.714**	0.922**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60
Y3	Pearson Correlation	0.625**	0.764**	1	0.732**	0.640**	0.854**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60
Y4	Pearson Correlation	0.647**	0.833**	0.732**	1	0.719**	0.899**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000		0.000	0.000
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60
Y5	Pearson Correlation	0.658**	0.714**	0.640**	0.719**	1	0.853**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000		0.000
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60
Y	Pearson Correlation	0.839**	0.922**	0.854**	0.899**	0.853**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60

Source: processed field data

In the table above. the results of the validity test show that all items in the employee performance variable statement (Y): numbers Y1, Y2, Y3, Y4 and Y5 are declared valid because all greater than 0.254.

4.4.2. Reliability Test

The indicator can be declared reliable on the basis of decision making, if the Cronbach's Alpha value (α) > 0.6 is obtained and not reliable if the Cronbach's Alpha value (α) \leq 0.6 is obtained. The results of the reliability test data on the research variables.

Table 7 Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Leadership	0.721	6
Training	0.830	5
Employee Performance	0.922	5

Source: processed field data

From the table above. it is found that all Cronbach's Alpha values are greater than 0.6 so that all variables are declared reliable.

4.4.3. Classic assumption test

Normality Test

The Kolmogrov Sminorv formula is used to determine the normality value of a data on the basis of decision making. ie if the value of sig. > 0.05. stated that the data was normally distributed and if the value of sig. ≤ 0.05 is declared not normally distributed. The results of calculating the normality of the data with SPSS are interpreted in the following table.

Table 8 Normality Test Results

		Unstandardized Residual
N		60
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	0.0000000
	Std. Deviation	2.82487321
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0.103
	Positive	0.103
	Negative	-0.055
Test Statistic		0.103
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		0.185 ^c

Source: processed field data

The table above shows the results of data processing where a significance value of 0.185 > 0.05 is obtained. then it is stated that the data has been normally distributed. meaning that the leadership and training variables on employee performance are stated to have normal distribution.

Multicollinearity Test

The basis used in making decisions on the multicollinearity test is that if the correlation between the independent variables is > 0.10 and VIF < 10 or not more than 10. it means that there is no multicollinearity. The results of the multicollinearity test are interpreted as follows.

The table is the result of the multicollinearity test which shows that the two independent variables have a Tolerance value > 0.10, each of which is 0.808 for X1 and 0.808 for X2. Meanwhile, the VIF value obtained by the independent variable < 10, each of which is worth 1.237 for X1 and 1.237 for X2. Referring to the results of the Tolerance and VIF values, it is concluded that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity between the independent variables in the regression model.

Table 9 Multicollinearity Test Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	6.773	2.523		2.685	.009		
	X1	0.280	0.117	0.281	2.394	0.020	0.808	1.237
	X2	0.436	0.120	0.425	3.617	0.001	0.808	1.237

Source: processed field data

Autocorrelation Test

One of the autocorrelation tests used is the Durbin-Waston model. The results of the calculation of the autocorrelation test are interpreted as follows:

Table 10 Autocorrelation Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	0.604	0.364	0.342	3.187	1.988

Source: processed field data

Based on the table above, the autocorrelation test obtained the Durbin-Watson value (d) is 1.988 with a significance of 5%, the number of samples is 60 ($n=60$), and the independent variable is 2 ($k=2$), so the value in the Durbin-Watson table (d) with a value of $dL = 1.514$ and a value of $dU = 1.651$. Because the d value of 1.988 is greater than the upper limit (dU) of 1.651 and less than $4 - 1.651$ (2.349), it is concluded that there is no autocorrelation.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The decision criteria in the Glejser test is if the significance value > 0.05 means that there is no heteroscedasticity. The results of the calculation of the heteroscedasticity test can be interpreted as follows.

Table 11 Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.972	1.434		2.769	0.008
	X1	0.006	0.066	0.013	0.091	0.928
	X2	-0.089	0.068	-0.189	-1.305	0.197

Source: processed field data

The results of the Heteroscedasticity test using the Glejser Test method can be seen in the table above. From the output, it is known that the significance value of all independent variables is > 0.05 so it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity problem in the regression model to be analysed.

4.5 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Based on the results of the analysis using the SPSS application, the regression results between the leadership variables (X1) and training (X2) on Employee Performance (Y) are as follows:

Table 12 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	6.773	2.523		2.685	0.009
	X1	0.280	0.117	0.281	2.394	0.020
	X2	0.436	0.120	0.425	3.617	0.001

Source: processed field data

From the output obtained. the regression equation model is obtained as follows:

$$Y = 6.773 + 0.280X1 + 0.436X2 + e$$

The regression equation model has the following meanings:

- The regression coefficients of the two independent variables (leadership and training) have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This means that every increase in the leadership and training variables will be followed by an increase in the Employee Performance variable.
- The training variable has a regression coefficient ($b_2 = 0.436$) which is the largest compared to the regression coefficient of the other independent variables, which means that employee performance is more dominantly influenced by the training variable.

4.6 Hypothesis Test

To prove the hypothesis in this study, it can be seen from the results of the partial test using the t test. This test aims to determine the significant effect between the independent variables on the dependent variable partially (individually). Basis of decision making:

- If the value of t-count $>$ t-table then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted.
- If the value of t-count \leq t-table, then H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected.

The t-count value can be seen from the regression results and for the t-table it is obtained from $df = n - k - 1$ ($60 - 3 - 1 = 56$) with a significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) the t-table is 2.003. The results of hypothesis testing are concluded as follows:

H1: Leadership has an effect on employee performance, the t-count value is 2.032 and the significance is 0.047, because the t-count value obtained is greater than 2.003 so that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. It means that the hypothesis which states that leadership has a positive and significant effect on the performance of the 'Start Up Tani Hub' employees is accepted.

H2: Training has an effect on employee performance, the t-count value is 4.258 and the significance is 0.000, because the t-count value obtained is greater than 2.003 so that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. It means that the hypothesis which states that training has a positive and significant effect on the performance of the 'Start Up Tani Hub' employees is accepted.

4.7 Managerial Implication

This study provides input to enrich the theory of the relationship between leadership and training on employee performance.

4. Conclusion

The results of research on the influence of leadership and training on employee performance can be concluded as follows:

- Leadership has an effect on employee performance with a t-count value of 2.032 and a significance of 0.047, because the t-count value obtained is greater than t-table so that leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.
- Training has an effect on employee performance with a t-count value of 4.258 and a significance of 0.000, because the t-count value obtained is greater than t-table so that training has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors wish to declare that none has any interest to disclose.

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